

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ARABIC TO STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the current problems of teaching Arabic, which every language learner encounters. The typical mistakes that occur when learning Arabic are considered. The range of issues in this article includes the issues of teaching pronunciation and phonetics of the Arabic language to students of higher educational institutions.

In the modern Arab world, we see a huge gap between the Arabic classical language, the guardian of which is the traditional school, and its oral form used by the Arab population. Literary, bookish and oral languages are not in live interaction, do not merge into a single system, which complicates their study.

The Arabic language is distinguished by its peculiar spelling and graphics, which presents some difficulties not only for students of the Arabic language, but also for its native speakers [4]. Let's focus on some of them.

Of particular difficulty is ة (hamza). For example, the connective ة at the beginning of a word is often written as a separator ة. And, conversely, the dividing line as a connecting one. There is a tendency to write ة in the middle and end of a word in places that contradict generally accepted rules. There is a tendency to write ة in the middle and end of a word in places that contradict generally accepted rules.

Due attention is not paid to the spelling of the sign ّ (tashdid). As a result, a letter falls out of the word and confusion arises in the meaning of some words.

There is also an incorrect spelling of a number of Arabic letters. For example, they neglect to write the diacritic point of the letter ّ, as a result it becomes a completely different letter — the letter ّ, or they use the letter ّ with only two dots, and it becomes the letter ّ. Very often, it (ta-marbuta) is written without dots and becomes the letter O at the end of a sentence, both in spelling and pronunciation.

The vowel ّ (алиф) at the end of a word may be mistakenly written long or short without taking into account the spelling rules. Often the letter ّ is written instead of the letter ّ and vice versa, and so on.

Thus, at present there is a widespread violation of the rules of Arabic spelling in fiction, journalism, business correspondence and even in official documents of government bodies.

Ignorance of the rules of Arabic morphology leads to incorrect spelling of a number of grammatical forms. Unfortunately, there is almost complete non-compliance with the rules of Arabic grammar in writing. First of all, it should be noted the incorrect use of cases in Arabic, which also leads to spelling errors and often refers to the dual number and the correct plural of the masculine gender, as well as to the spelling of numerals. The postposition of the adjective name in the definition function in relation to the word being defined is not respected. Attention is not paid to the category of determinativity, namely certainty and uncertainty.

Structural, grammatical and stylistic violations in the construction of Arabic sentences lead to the replacement of the literary language with spoken in written speech, which is unacceptable. As a result, the Arabic language loses its expressiveness and ability to emotionally influence the reader.

Currently, when teaching Arabic literary language, insufficient attention is paid to punctuation, which makes it much more difficult to understand the meaning of the text, as a result of which the connection of words in a sentence is lost.

Some scholars argue that punctuation marks are not an integral part of Arabic linguistics, but are borrowed from other languages. However, the neglect of punctuation marks leads to a deviation from the classical norms of the Arabic literary language.

Some scholars argue that punctuation marks are not an integral part of Arabic linguistics, but are borrowed from other languages. However, the neglect of punctuation marks leads to a deviation from the classical norms of the Arabic literary language. As you know, punctuation marks entered the Arabic language from European languages, which contributed to its development. It became possible to clearly define the beginning and end of a phrase, connect sentences with each other, defining their syntactic and semantic relationships, a variety of intonation models expressing the goals of speech (question, surprise, denial, sorrow, motivation, warning, etc.), becoming an integral component of modern Arabic writing. Currently, the absence of punctuation marks is equated with syntactic and grammatical errors, as this makes it difficult for the reader to understand the meaning of the text due to the confusion of expressions and sentences, there is ambiguity and confusion of meaning, the author's words are not separated from direct speech and quotations [3].

Nevertheless, it should be noted that, despite the borrowed nature of punctuation marks in the Arabic language, some scientific sources indicate their existence in ancient times. For example, in Tajweed there were special signs of the beginning and stopping of reading the verses of the Quran, which were used by scientists to correctly read and understand their meanings, comprehending their syntactic and semantic connection with each other. This can also include the research of linguists regarding separation and connection, stopping and pausing, connecting and resuming, presenting the whole variety of sound intonations following a certain meaning: urges, intimidation, warnings, exhortations, questions, experiences, and so on [5].

Thus, in the modern written speech of the Arabic language, the use of orthographic norms of the spoken language prevails to the detriment of literary ones. There are also pronunciation inaccuracies in the fields of education, science, politics, economics, mass media, advertising, and so on, which should use the Arabic literary language.

The most common mistakes are related to the absence of diacritical marks (vocalizations) in the letter, which affect the correct pronunciation. The indistinct pronunciation of some letters is also noted. Thus, as a result of the fact that millions of people listen to radio and watch television programs every day, they are constantly exposed to distorted forms of pronunciation of the above-mentioned letters, and involuntarily adopt them, using them in everyday speech. This is especially true for children; whose brains are most susceptible to receiving information [2].

There is a pronunciation of the connective hamza as a dividing one. The correct pronunciation of the connective hamza is very rare. This also manifests itself when pronouncing a certain article. Currently, the absence of pronunciation h and the ending of pronunciation on the previous letter in the speech stream of radio and television presenters, even by philologists, is considered the norm. It is becoming common to use conversational pronunciation skills when mentioning numerals and calculable.

There is also a truncation of the endings of words and their pronunciation with a sukun in the flow of speech. This is typical for the speech of famous writers, scientists, journalists, radio and television announcers, as well as heads of specialized linguistic institutes.

Dialects permeate fiction and journalism. The literary language is being replaced by a spoken one, however, the reverse process, namely, the replacement of the spoken language with a literary one, does not occur. This can be observed in many radio and television shows, where local dialects prevail, so that the use of literary language in them is minimized.

Discrepancies between literary language and dialects exist at all levels — phonological, morphological, lexematical and syntactic.

There has been a tendency for native Arabic words to be gradually replaced by foreign borrowings without special need. Although it should be noted that the Arabic equivalents are simpler in form, easier in pronunciation, deeper in meaning and more harmonious for the listener.

It comes to the point that some Arab settlements receive foreign names using the Latin alphabet, ignoring the rich potential and peculiar calligraphy of the Arabic literary language. This can lead to total dependence on Western culture and civilization in everything.

Pronunciation errors also apply to a number of grammatical forms. For example, when matching the middle letter of three-letter verbs of the past and present tense, as well as the imperative mood, which is caused by ignorance of the morphological forms of verb breeds.

Errors in the use of present tense forms are not uncommon, arising from the lack of differentiation between three- and four-letter verbs.

Even in the speech of the speakers, there is an incorrect intonation of speech, which leads to a distortion of the meaning of the utterance. For example, the descending tone characteristic of the end of a sentence is used instead of the ascending tone, which indicates the incompleteness of the utterance. Interrogative sentences are pronounced as narrative or vice versa. A speech expressing sorrow, pain and sadness is delivered with inappropriate enthusiasm in this case. Or a speech full of pride and hope is delivered in the expressionless cold tone of the announcer.

Intonation, as it is known, is "the unity of interrelated components: melody, intensity, duration, tempo of speech and timbre of utterance." Together with stress, intonation forms

the prosodic system of the language. Intonation is an important means of forming an utterance and revealing its meaning. In an utterance, intonation performs the following functions: distinguishes the communicative types of utterance — motivation, question, exclamation, narration, implication (implication); distinguishes parts of the utterance according to their semantic importance; forms the utterance into a single whole, simultaneously dividing it into rhythmic groups and syntagmas; expresses specific emotions; reveals the subtext of the utterance; characterizes the speaker and the situation communication" [1].

It goes without saying that all these remarks do not detract from the value of the Arabic heritage, but ignoring the living language creates serious difficulties in the semantic interpretation of homogeneous and structurally similar words. The main danger lies in determining the meanings of words not on the basis of their functioning in the modern era, but on the basis of their understanding in the distant past. And finally, if we recognize language as a system, then it is necessary to recognize the consistency of vocabulary, because it is difficult to imagine a system some parts of which are systemic and others are unsystematic.

Thus, the erroneous pronunciation of certain lexical and grammatical forms is one of the main factors influencing the distance of the Arabic literary language from its classical norms.

Thus, the erroneous pronunciation and spelling of certain lexical and grammatical forms is one of the main factors that contribute to difficulties in mastering written speech, leading to typical mistakes that students make in written speech, as well as moving away from the classical norms of the Arabic literary language. Learning Arabic as a foreign language is an opportunity to penetrate the world of the arab East, another layer of worldview and mentality, the opportunity to communicate with the political and cultural world.

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